

DIGITAL BRAND LOCAL PRODUCT KREESANG 354 THROUGH INSTAGRAM ACCOUNT @KREESANG2WSSAQ354 IN INCREASING BRAND AWARENESS

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Abstract

This research aims to analyze the use of digital branding strategies on the local product Kreesang 354 through the Instagram account @Kreesang354 in increasing brand awareness. In the current digital era, social media has become an important platform in product marketing, especially for local brands that want to introduce their products to a wider audience. This study examines how Kreesang 354 utilizes Instagram as a tool to build brand image and increase brand awareness among consumers. The method used in this research is a qualitative approach with a case study on the Kreesang 354 Instagram account. Data were obtained through direct observation of the uploaded content, interaction with the audience, as well as analysis of the engagement rate and frequency of interactions occurring on the platform. In addition, interviews with the administrators of the Kreesang 354 Instagram account and several consumers were also conducted to deepen the understanding of the digital branding strategies implemented. The research results show that Kreesang 354 has successfully utilized Instagram as an effective medium to introduce their products by using various features such as feed, stories, and IGTV to create engaging content. Additionally, the use of influencers and collaborations with various parties also contributed to increasing brand interaction and exposure. Thus, this research concludes that Instagram has a significant impact on increasing brand awareness for the local product Kreesang 354.

Keywords: Brand Awareness, Digital Brand, Instagram, Kreesang 354.

INTRODUCTION

The agricultural sector is currently one of the areas continuously pursued for agribusiness development in order to enhance modern agriculture. Indonesia, as an agrarian country, derives much of its livelihood from farming, which is why the agricultural sector continues to be relied upon to support the national economic growth. According to (Isbah & Iyan, 2016), almost the majority of Indonesia's population lives in rural areas as farmers. Agribusiness development in Indonesia is supported by natural resources and human resources that are very supportive in terms of quantity but still lacking in quality. This is because agribusiness actors, who are predominantly farmers residing in rural areas, still have relatively low levels of education, with low skills and low ability to access technology, which becomes a hindrance in agribusiness development in Indonesia.

Industrial development in construction is seen as an effort to improve the quality of human resources (among other things by increasing their productivity) and their ability to optimally utilize natural resources and other production capacities. One another, this must be accompanied by efforts to expand the scope of various types of human activities. According to (Budihardjo et al., 2020), the economic growth of a region is more about a goods and services that prosper its people so that the regional economy can advance. One of the food crop commodities that can support the establishment of several industries is the banana. Bananas have a wide range of uses because, in addition to being raw materials for food and non-food industries, they are also consumed in households.

According to (Suyanti et al., 2016), banana chips are chips made from processed bananas that are fried in a special way. Kreesang 354 is the result of innovative thinking that presents banana chips by utilizing local bananas. Kreesang 354 uses cere' bananas, which are a characteristic of the Soppeng region in South Sulawesi. The process begins with the selection of raw cere' bananas. The method of making it is as follows: the bananas are peeled, then sliced with a knife to a thickness of 4 mm, and then soaked in cold water. Drain the soaked bananas, and once dry, they can be fried. With the increasing popularity of banana chips, consumer demand is also rising.

Kreesang 354 is one example of utilizing social media, especially Instagram, to increase brand awareness. According to (Thoyibie, 2014), social media is content containing information, created by individuals utilizing publishing technology, very easily accessible, and intended to facilitate communication, influence, and interaction with peers and the general public. The practice of marketing through social media is beginning to develop and is being used as a tool for marketing a company's product brands and brands.

In the increasingly dominant digital era, an interesting phenomenon is occurring in the business world, namely how local products like Kreesang 354 banana chips can leverage the power of social media, especially Instagram accounts, to enhance their brand awareness. Kreesang 354, as one of the local banana chip producers, is introducing its products to a wider market through a smart digital marketing approach.

The importance of community support and awareness for local products like Kreesang 354 banana chips cannot be underestimated. Local products often struggle to compete with larger and more well-known international brands. However, with the increasing awareness of the importance of supporting local products for local economic growth and sustainability, the community is now more open to local products. Kreesang 354, which has now become an example of utilizing social media, has transformed banana chips, previously considered an ordinary product, into a nationally recognized brand.

Instagram, as one of the leading social media platforms, plays a central role in Kreesang 354's digital marketing strategy. With this platform, they can share attractive product visuals and creative content that have helped them attract attention and gain loyal followers. The power of visuals in marketing has become one of the keys to Kreesang 354's success, mastering the art of taking eye-catching product photos and making them the main attraction on their Instagram account.

In addition, Instagram also provides an interactive platform for communicating with customers. Through comments, direct messages, and other interactive features, Kreesang 354 can directly interact with their consumers, answer questions, receive feedback, and even gain insights into what consumers want from their products. The impact of this marketing approach is that local products like Kreesang 354 can now reach potential customers across the region, no longer limited to specific geographical areas. Instagram users from various backgrounds and locations can easily discover and interact with this brand.

In addition, the active role of consumers sharing their experiences through social media also contributes to promoting this brand to their own social networks. When someone posts a photo of the Kreesang 354 banana chips they enjoyed or gives a positive review, it creates a domino effect where their friends who see it might also become interested in trying the product.

This phenomenon motivated researchers to study Kreesang 354. Kreesang 354 was established in December 2022, with its production house located at Jalan Mannuruki 9 No. 28 G. Kreesang 354's production house was founded by Fahmuddin and Auliah Nurul Qalbi, who have 5 employees. The marketing strategy of Kreesang 354 started with door-to-door sales. From door-to-door sales, it achieved sales results of approximately 5 million per month. The last one is sales through social media, namely Instagram, which with using Instagram social media sales can increase brand awareness.

Further research will delve into the digital marketing strategies implemented by Kreesang 354, particularly how they interact with consumers through the Instagram platform, and its impact on public perception of local products. This research is expected to provide deeper insights into the role of Instagram in enhancing brand awareness of local products.

In this context, this research uses the Three I Theory by Deirdre Breakendride, which views information as the delivery of messages that is not limited to company profiles or brochures, but rather emphasizes the importance of conveying information that aligns

with the audience's expectations regarding the attributes and characteristics of an online brand. Interactivity, as explained by Breakendridge, has become an important new dimension for products that were established before the digital era. Therefore, Kreesang 354's digital marketing strategy on Instagram needs to pay attention to the aspect of interactivity in order to provide an effective experience for consumers.

Additionally, the concept of instinct is also a key factor in digital marketing efforts. Instinct includes the effort to not imitate other brands, both in content and marketing efforts, in order to create a significant difference from other companies. Thus, Kreesang 354 needs to ensure that their marketing strategy on Instagram is not only unique but also aligns with their brand values and identity.

Through this research, it is expected to reveal how these aspects work together in the context of Kreesang 354's digital marketing on Instagram and how this impacts public perception of local products. The entire research will provide a more comprehensive understanding of Instagram's role in enhancing brand awareness related to local products.

With this background, one can understand the importance of social media, particularly Instagram, in changing public perceptions of local products such as Kreesang 354 banana chips. This company has become one of the examples of utilizing social media as a powerful marketing tool to reach a wider market and gain greater brand recognition. This is not only beneficial for Kreesang as a company, but also inspires other local products to adopt similar digital marketing strategies to gain greater attention and enhance their brand awareness. Based on this, the author is interested in taking the title "Digital Brand of Local Product Kreesang 354 Through Instagram Account @kreesang354 in Increasing Brand Awareness," and it is hoped that it can serve as motivation for other entrepreneurs to improve their businesses.

RESEARCH METHOD

Research methods are activities or systematic investigation methods that are properly organized and continuously interconnected to solve a problem (Adnani, 2021). In this study, a descriptive qualitative research method is used to understand phenomena directly and in-depth, thereby obtaining evidence from the collected data. In this study, the researcher used data collection techniques in the form of interviews, observations, and documentation. According to Saryono, qualitative research is a type of research used to investigate, discover, describe, and explain the quality or characteristics of social influences that cannot be explained, measured, or described through a quantitative approach (Abdussamad, 2021).

This research discusses digital brands. This research uses the three I theory by Deirdre Breakendridge. First, Information, which is conveying what meets the expectations of the audience from an online brand, depends on the attributes and characteristics of the brand. The information can include; Products, Product Purchases, Collaborations, Exhibitions, Giveaways, and Office Activities. Second, Interactivity is a degree in communication

activities where participants can exchange messages. The interactivity can include; Communication with Consumers, Providing Feedback, Reposting Followers' Posts, Endorsements, and Competitors. The third, Instinct, is the effort to not imitate other companies' brands either in content or marketing efforts, so there is a distinction from other companies. That instinct includes: Instagram Feed, Instagram Story, Instagram Highlight, Instagram Shopping, and Instagram Insight.

The Research Subject is something that holds a central position because it is within the research subject that the data regarding the variables being studied is located and observed by the researcher (Arikunto, 2014). The subject of this research is the social media of @kreesang354 and all parties who can provide the information needed by the researcher to address the issues outlined above and the events in the field in order to obtain accurate data. Besides the subjects in solving the problems of this research, the author has several informants. Informants are individuals who provide the information needed for this research (Arikunto, 2014). The informants for the research are Fahmuiddiin as the Vendor CEO, Auliah Nurul Qalbi as the Unit Manager & Finance, Ropiuddin as the Product Photography & Content from Kreesang 354, and the customers.

Based on the Indonesian Dictionary, an object is a case, thing, or person that becomes the topic of discussion (Fajar et al., 2020). According to Husein Umar, the research object explains what and who the object is, as well as the time and place where the research is conducted, or in other words, the research object is the focus of a study. The research object is based on theories that align with the study. Meanwhile, the object of this research is the issue that becomes the focus of the study, namely the digital brand of Kreesang 354 products through the Instagram account @kreesang354.

In this study, the researcher used three data collection strategies: interviews, Instagram account observations, and documentation. With a descriptive qualitative approach that provides a depiction of the actual situation. Data analysis is conducted starting from: problem identification, data collection, and post-data collection. According to the model created by Miles & Huberman (Miles et al., 2014), there are four schemes as follows:

1. Data collection, the author searches for data while analyzing it because they can identify which data needs to be collected and determine which method should be used for the next stage.
2. Data reduction, defined as the process of selecting, focusing, validating data, and transforming raw data obtained in the field.
3. Data presentation. Data or documents obtained in the field need to be presented in graphic, chart, or matrix form to combine information into an integrated format.
4. Drawing conclusions. The final stage in the research process after data presentation and data reduction have been completed. This stage involves the organization of notes, the direction of cause and effect, and patterns that are carried out in a systematic manner. Or it can be interpreted as a final

conclusion that is initially written in an unclear state and then develops into a strong statement within a phenomenon (Syahroi & Pratiwi, 2024).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Brand becomes a crucial element for a company because it influences the sustainability of products or brands in an increasingly competitive market. Brand is a fundamental marketing strategy that every company must have. Brand encompasses brand identity, including visual characteristics, perception, impression, credibility, logo, and company narrative.

The shift from offline marketing strategies (before) to online marketing through social media like Instagram shows Kreesang 354's adaptation to the times and digital marketing trends. Previously, this business relied on direct sales using the door-to-door method, which was effective in the local market. However, due to limited reach, Kreesang 354 realized the need to explore digital media to overcome these limitations. Through the use of Instagram, Kreesang 354 not only expanded their market but also utilized various features that allow direct interaction with consumers, increased brand awareness, and provided opportunities for further development in product marketing more broadly and effectively. Thus, Kreesang 354's move to shift their marketing focus to digital platforms has become a strategy that greatly supports the sustainability and growth of their brand. Kreesang 354 was established in January 2023 with a production house located at Jalan Mannuruki 9 No. 28 G. This business was founded by Fahmuddin and Auliah Nurul Qalbi, supported by five employees. Initially, Kreesang 354 started its marketing strategy with a door-to-door method, which allowed them to directly reach consumers and introduce their banana chip products to the local market. This approach proved to be quite effective, with sales reaching around 5 million per month. Nevertheless, they feel the need to further expand their market reach.

Seeing the existing opportunities, Kreesang 354 began shifting their marketing focus to social media platforms, particularly Instagram. By optimizing Instagram, they can reach a wider consumer base and increase brand visibility. The use of social media allows them to interact directly with consumers, build closer relationships, and introduce their products to a larger audience. Engaging and informative content, such as recipe videos and exclusive promotions, also boosts brand awareness.

Additionally, the marketing strategy through Instagram allows Kreesang 354 to reach a more diverse market. By increasing engagement through more consistent and interactive posts, Kreesang 354 can attract the attention of more consumers, both domestically and internationally. This helps them to market their products more effectively, increase the number of customers, and strengthen their brand image in the market.

The success of this social media marketing strategy is also evident in the significant increase in sales. With professional management of their Instagram account and a focus on relevant content, Kreesang 354 not only succeeded in introducing their products to new

consumers but also created a loyal and actively engaged community. As a result, their sales skyrocketed and Kreesang 354's brand awareness became even stronger among consumers.

In 2022, Kreesang 354 successfully reached 5 million in brand awareness through the Instagram account @Kreesang354. In 2023, the results increased to 6 million, showing an increase of 1 million or 20% compared to the previous year. This increase indicates that the marketing efforts in the first year successfully attracted a larger audience and significantly boosted brand awareness.

In 2024, Kreesang 354's brand awareness increased again to 8 million, with a rise of 2 million or 33.33% compared to 2023. The larger increase in 2024 indicates that the marketing strategies implemented are becoming more effective and successfully reaching more people. Overall, Kreesang 354 has experienced stable and positive growth each year, with a higher percentage increase in the second year compared to the first year.

In its online strategy, Kreesang 354 utilizes the Instagram platform to build and strengthen its brand. The use of Instagram provides significant benefits because the audience on that platform aligns with the target market set by Kreesang 354. By building a brand through Instagram, the company not only increases brand awareness but also helps consumers in the decision-making process, while providing opportunities for consumers to give constructive feedback to sellers to continuously improve the quality of services and products (Hamdan et al., 2017).

Communication media, both online and offline, are formed through marketing communication activities aimed at creating brand awareness, especially in the increasingly developing digital economy era.

In the digital branding carried out by Kreesang 354 through the Instagram account @kreesang354, this research adopts the concept of the 3 "i" theory, namely information, interactivity, and instinct. The research results show that Kreesang 354 on the Instagram account @kreesang354 provides information about products through posts. They also interact with followers through Q&A sessions, providing space for comments and suggestions. Kreesang 354 differentiates itself from its competitors through its signature banana chip products and unique post themes.

1. Information

Research results show that Kreesang 354 utilizes Instagram as a medium to provide relevant information to meet the needs and answer the questions of consumers and followers. The information conveyed through Instagram is designed to be easily understood, practical, and engaging. With followers from various backgrounds, Kreesang 354 ensures that the content provided remains simple, informative, and attention-grabbing.

The main goal of every business is to build brand awareness, as a person's interest in purchasing a product is greatly influenced by recommendations and direct experiences (Keller, 2013).

Kreesang 354 focuses its brand more on Instagram than on other social media platforms. The use of Instagram is considered more advantageous because its strong visual

aspect is supported by various features that enrich the brand.

Kreesang 354 uses its Instagram account to convey information related to products, purchasing processes, collaborations, exhibition events, and giveaway programs. The information is presented through various features available on Instagram such as Instagram Story, regular posts, linktree, highlights, and Instagram Live.

Information is presented regularly on the Instagram account @kreesang354 every day with diverse themes. There is a special schedule where every day there is at least one feed post or several feed posts, and at least five Instagram Stories. Kreesang 354 always updates its Instagram content in an effort to achieve a high level of user engagement.

Based on the observations and interviews conducted by the researcher, the information presented through the Instagram account @kreesang354 has met the expected standards. The information conveyed on that account is considered sufficiently relevant and capable of addressing the common needs often experienced by users or consumers.

2. Interactivity

Based on the research that has been conducted, Kreesang 354 is known to establish relationships and attract public attention through various forms of interaction. One of the methods used is through interaction with the public on social media, particularly Instagram. The choice of Instagram as a branding medium is based on several strategic considerations.

Through Instagram, Kreesang 354 can not only assist consumers in the decision-making process but also create space for consumers to provide constructive feedback, allowing the company to continuously improve the quality of its services and products in the future (Hanindharputri & Pradnyanita, 2021).

For online interactivity, Kreesang 354 uses the Instagram account @kreesang354 by responding to comments, both in Direct Messages (DM) and on posts. Although the response to comments on posts is not yet optimal, compared to a few months ago, interactivity in the past few months has shown significant improvement. The more often the Kreesang 354 admin responds to comments, the higher the public's enthusiasm to leave comments, whether in the form of praise, complaints, or questions.

3. Instinct

The research conducted has yielded findings that the use of the Instinct theory provides an understanding of how Kreesang 354 enhances its brand awareness. Kreesang 354 is a producer of banana chips that uses high-quality banana raw materials.

Kreesang 354 has distinctive features that set it apart from competitors, both in terms of products, promotional methods, and the appearance of its Instagram feed. Kreesang 354 continues to strive to keep up with the times to remain relevant and competitive. Kreesang 354's banana chips are designed to be enjoyed by all ages, thanks to their superior quality and taste. These factors have allowed Kreesang 354 to endure and thrive to this day. Brand awareness is the ability of potential buyers to recognize and remember a brand as part of a specific product category. Strategies to increase brand awareness must be able to explain the uniqueness of the brand and highlight its differences from competitors. The main goal of every business is to build brand awareness, because a

person's decision to purchase a product is greatly influenced by recommendations and direct experiences (Kotler, 2014).

Using Instagram as a branding medium requires Kreesang 354 to continuously keep up with the times and create content that is relevant for all ages and remains engaging over time. Some content created without imitating similar products includes: the feed theme on Instagram @kreesang354, which features a cute, modern, and minimalist theme while highlighting its products. For example, creating a feed about product usage. Kreesang 354's Instagram must reflect its cute characteristics, starting from the feed, colors, captions, models, and all elements on Instagram that should align with Kreesang 354's traits or slogan. Consistency in maintaining the distinctive features of Kreesang 354 will facilitate branding and help the public recognize the Kreesang 354 brand.

CONCLUSION

Based on the discussion of the results and the research description as well as the observations conducted by the researcher, it can be concluded that the digital branding of the local banana chip product through the Instagram account in increasing brand awareness includes several aspects:

1. The digital branding of Kreesang 354 focuses on maintaining and strengthening the brand by providing a positive perspective to the public, thereby building and enhancing brand awareness and consumer loyalty towards Kreesang 354 products. The result is positive feedback from the public.
2. Kreesang 354 not only focuses on improving the quality of its products but also on enhancing personal quality and all aspects within Kreesang 354, such as the way information is conveyed, maintaining good relationships with the public, and preserving brand identity. This approach can also significantly increase product sales.
3. In increasing brand awareness of the local banana chip product Kreesang 354 through Instagram, Kreesang 354 is active in presenting engaging information on the Instagram account @kreesang354, building good relationships with the public by enhancing interactivity, and differentiating itself by highlighting its unique characteristics. This approach can also increase product sales.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Abdussamad, Z. (2021). *Metode Penelitian Kualitatif*. Makassar : CV Syakir Media Press. 1–224.
- Abidin, Y. (2019). *Konsep Dasar Bahasa Indonesia* (Tarmizi, Ed.). PT Bumi Aksara. Adnani, K. (2021). *Metodologi Penelitian Komunikasi Kualitatif Dan Kuantitatif*. 1–142. eprints.iain-surakarta.ac.id
- Andata, C. P., Iflah, Kurnia, & Putri, S. A. (2022). Pengaruh Media Sosial Dalam Meningkatkan Brand Awareness “Somethinc” Pada Pengguna Instagram. *Jurnal Komunikasi*, 13(2), 84–92. <https://doi.org/10.31294/jkom>
- Arikunto, S. (2014). *Prosedur Penelitian Suatu Pendekatan Praktik*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- Atmoko, B. D. (2014). *Instagram Handbook Tips Fotografi Ponsel*. Jakarta : Media Kita

(Vol. 6, Issue 3). Onilne.

- Budihardjo, A., Arianti, F., & Mas'ud, F. (2020). Pengaruh Investasi, Tenaga Kerja, Dan Indeks Pembangunan Manusia Terhadap PDRB (Studi Kasus Kabupaten/Kota di Provinsi Jawa Tengah Tahun 2016-2018). *DIPONEGORO JOURNAL OF ECONOMICS*, Vol 9, No 2, 1–9. <https://ejournal2.undip.ac.id/index.php/dje>
- Bungin, B. (2022). Analisis Data Penelitian Kualitatif. 1–288.
- Fajar, M. L. Nur., Agus, Sriyanto., & SOS, S. (2020). Cyber Branding Tumurun Private Museum Solo Melalui Instagram Dalam Meningkatkan Brand Awareness Pengunjung. PhD Thesis. IAIN SURAKARTA.
- Hanindhauptri, M. A., & Pradnyanita, A. A. S. I. (2021). Konten Visual Instagram Sebagai Strategi Pemasaran UMKM Baru. *Prosiding SNADES 2021 - Kebangkitan Desain & New Media: Membangun Indonesia Di Era Pandemi*, 285–292. <https://www.instagram.com/omosnackbali>,
- Isbah, U., & Iyan, R. Y. (2016). Analisis peran sektor pertanian dalam perekonomian dan kesempatan kerja di Provinsi Riau. *Jurnal Sosial Ekonomi Pembangunan*, 7 (19), 45–54. festiva.ejournal.unri.ac.id
- Khanza, G. (2020). Analisis Digital Marketing Melalui Media Sosial Terhadap Brand Awareness Di Desa Wisata Gabungan, Turi, Sleman. STP AMPTA.
- Kotler, P. (2014). Manajemen Pemasaran. etheses.iainkediri.ac.id
- Kriyantono, R. (2014). Teknik Praktik Riset Komunikasi Kuantitatif dan Kualitatif: Disertai contoh praktis skripsi, tesis, dan disertai riset media, Public Relation, Advertising, Komunikasi Organisasi, Komunikasi Pemasaran.
- Kurniawan, M. A. (2021). Perencanaan Video Promosi Desa Puhsarang sebagai Upaya Meningkatkan Brand Recall.
- Kusumastuti, A., & Khoiron, A. M. (2019). Metode Penelitian Kualitatif (F. Annisya & Sukarno, Eds.). Lembaga Pendidikan Sukarno Pressindo (LPSP).
- Miles, M. B., Huberman, A. M., & Saldana, J. (2014). *Qualitative Data Analysis, A Methods Sourcebook* (H. Salmon, Ed.). SAGE Publications.
- Mulyasa. (2022). Manajemen Pendidikan Karakter (D. Ispurwanti, Ed.). PT Bumi Aksara.
- Nugraha, S. D. U. (2019). Strategi Digital Branding Media Sosial Instagram PT. Kereta Api Indonesia (Studi Deskriptif Kualitatif Pada Akun Instagram @keretaapikita). Universitas Telkom.
- Nuraviananda, M. T. (2022). Cyber Branding “Bakar Production” Dalam Membentuk Brand Image Sebagai Ketoprak Modern.
- Paramitha, H., & Doho, Y. D. B. (2021). Pengaruh Konten Instagram Ads @Luxebarbershop Terhadap Peningkatan Brand Awareness. *Journal of Research on Business and Tourism*, 1(2), 119. <https://doi.org/10.37535/104001220213>
- Pragita, Y. (2022). Digital Branding Norma Coffee Melalui Konten Kreatif Di Instagram @normacoffee.id. Universitas Islam Negeri Sultan Syarif Kasim.
- Riduwan. (2014). Metode Observasi dan Penelitian. Rineka Cipta.
- Simarmata, L. F. (2019). Cyber Branding Clothing Line Nadjani (Studi Kasus Cyber Branding Clothing Line Nadjani Melalui Akun Instagram @nadjaniindonesia Dalam Membangun Brand Loyalty Konsumennya) [Universitas Komputer Indonesia]. <https://doi.org/http://elibrary.unikom.ac.id>
- Sugiyono. (2016). Metode Penelitian Pendidikan Pendekatan Kuantitatif, Kualitatif dan R&D. Bandung : Alfabeta.,.
- Susilo, A. (2020). Aktivitas Cyber Public Relations Pegipegi.com Dalam Meningkatkan Brand Awareness Cyber Public Relations Activities Pegipegi.com In Improving Brand

- Awareness. *Jurnal Spektrum Komunikasi*, 8(1).
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.37826/spektrum.v8i1.61>
- Suyanti, Ahmad, & Supriyadi. (2016). *Pisang, Budidaya, Pengolahan, Dan Prospek Pasar*. Jakarta: Penebar Swadaya.
- Syahroi, M. R., & Pratiwi, R. Z. B. (2024). Cyber Branding Rumah Budaya Kratonan dalam Membentuk Citra Community Center Kota Surakarta. *Jurnal Publikasi Ilmu Komunikasi Media Dan Cinema*, 6(2).
- Syaifuddin, W. K. (2022). Strategi Branding Instagram @Santri Design Community Sebagai Brand Awareness.
- Syam, A., Rakib, M., & Yani, I. (2020). Pengaruh Literasi Kewirausahaan dan Karakter Wirausaha terhadap Keberhasilan Usaha Kecil. *Journal of Economic Education and Entrepreneurship Studies*, 2, 65–77.
- Thoyibie, L. (2014). Psikologi Social Media. <https://doi.org/10.35130/jrimk> Wulandari, H. (2022). Digital Branding Di Media Sosial Instagram Bekasi Keren (@kotabekasikeren) Dalam Pembentukan Citra Kota Bekasi. Universitas Islam“45” Bekasi.
- Yunus, U. (2022). *Digital Branding Teori Dan Praktek*. Simbiosis Rekatama Media.